

Strelitzia juncea Rush-leaved strelitzia

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

Phylum: Magnoliophyta

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Estimated genome size: 739 million DNA base pairs (0.74 Gigabases)

Organism size: One to two meters in height

Distribution:

The rush-leaved strelitzia is indigenous to South Africa and occurs in sparse populations near Uitenhage, Patensie, and north of Gqeberha in the Eastern Cape. It grows in dry, open habitats.

Importance:

The rush-leaved strelitzia or narrow-leaved bird of paradise is a striking, drought-resistant plant indigenous to South Africa. It has unique cylindrical leaves and vibrant flowers, is slow-growing and adapted to semi-arid conditions. Wild populations face threats from habitat loss and illegal collection for horticultural purposes.

PromethION Sequencing Report: Output: 19.82 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 13.25 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome length: 592.36 million bases (0.59 Gigabases)

BUSCO completeness score (single and duplicated genes): 98.8%

[Single: 57.6%, Duplicated: 41.2%]

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